

Implementation of innovative projects: a systematic approach to organizing the initial stages

E.Y. Khrustalev,

д-р экон. наук, проф., главный научный сотрудник, Центральный экономико-математический институт РАН (e-mail: stalev777@yandex.ru)

S.N. Larin,

канд. техн. наук, старший научный сотрудник, ведущий научный сотрудник, Центральный экономико-математический институт РАН (e-mail: sergey77707@rambler.ru)

O.E. Khrustalev,

канд. экон. наук, старший научный сотрудник, Центральный экономико-математический институт РАН (e-mail: stalev777@yandex.ru)

Аннотация. Нередко инициаторы инновационных проектов на начальных этапах их реализации допускают стратегические ошибки. Некоторые из них связаны с недостаточным уровнем коммуникаций между предполагаемыми участниками таких проектов. Совокупность указанных факторов предопределяет низкую эффективность инвестиций в инновационный сектор реальной экономики. Авторы считают целесообразным использовать разработанную ими типологию инновационных проектов на начальных этапах их реализации. Это позволит повысить эффективность взаимодействия между потенциальными инвесторами и исполнителями инновационных проектов. В работе обоснованы подходы к обоснованию актуальности реализации инновационного проекта, определена очередность этапов подготовки инвестиционных планов. Для принятия решения о выборе конкретного варианта проекта и его дальнейшей реализации предлагается использовать методологический аппарат теории игр.

Abstract. Often, initiators of innovative projects make strategic mistakes at the initial stages of their implementation. Some of them are associated with an insufficient level of communication between the prospective participants of such projects. The combination of these factors predetermines the low efficiency of investments in the innovative sector of the real economy. The authors consider it advisable to use the typology of innovative projects they developed at the initial stages of their implementation. This will improve the efficiency of interaction between potential investors and executors of innovative projects. The paper substantiates approaches to substantiating the relevance of implementing an innovative project, and determines the sequence of stages in preparing investment plans. To make a decision on choosing a specific version of the project and its further implementation, it is proposed to use the methodological apparatus of game theory.

Ключевые слова: инновационный проект, реализация, системный подход, типология, начальные этапы, организация.

Keywords: innovative project, implementation, system approach, typology, initial stages, organization.

Introduction

The significant innovative potential of the Russian economy and its financial system is largely ensured by investments of high-tech and knowledge-intensive corporations and enterprises in innovative projects of varying importance and duration [1, 2]. However, with the development of market methods of economic management at the beginning of the 21st century, the interactions of these participants in innovative projects have become much more complex [3, 4]. This is due to the fact that banks prefer to direct significant funds to finance trading operations and speculation in the securities and currency markets. Loans allocated by banks for the development of industrial enterprises are often used to finance mergers and acquisitions of companies, rather than their innovative development. This not only slows down

economic growth, but also, according to the head of the Central Bank of Russia, creates additional risks for the innovative transformation of the domestic economy [5].

The preferences of high-tech and knowledge-intensive corporations and enterprises are based on the fact that investments in innovative projects are by their nature significantly more risky compared to operations in the real estate markets and various financial instruments. In turn, banks are not eager to finance innovative projects that involve specific assets, innovative technologies and products with unknown market prospects. In order to make a decision, it is important for all project participants to correctly determine the return on investment, payback period, risks and other expected indicators for the implementation of innovative projects. At the same time, the

main problem is often that the project initiator is unable to convince potential investors and implementers of the effectiveness of the proposed technical and organizational solutions.

In addition, as practice shows, many initiators of innovative projects make strategic mistakes at the initial stages of their development. Such mistakes include the following:

- the lack of free production space at the enterprise required for the installation of new technological equipment is not taken into account;
- overestimation of demand for the enterprise's new products;
- the lack of technical and/or financial capacity for the enterprise to implement the release of new products is not taken into account;
- insufficient justification for the proposed technical and technological solutions for the production of new products;
- ignoring other critically important problems of innovative development of enterprises.

As a rule, mistakes made at the initial stages of innovative projects can lead to irreversible consequences, among which the easiest can be considered the refusal of potential investors to finance the work.

The above circumstances determine the relevance of this work.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to substantiate the feasibility of using the typology of innovative projects proposed by the authors at the initial stages of their development and implementation. This will improve the efficiency of interaction between potential investors and project implementers.

Materials and methods of research

The project initiator needs to choose one investor from among many different investors or form a consortium of several potential investors that will be able to finance the project on terms acceptable to all its participants. It is important to determine what type the project belongs.

To solve the problem of increasing the efficiency of investments in innovative projects, the authors used a system approach, which provides for the decomposition of the object of study and its system analysis, based on the results of which the sequence of implementation of project activities is established. To make decisions on the selection of projects, methods of game theory, forecasting theory and mathematical modeling were used.

At the initial stage, the project initiator must determine the type of his technical or organizational proposal and the scope of its application. A significant portion of projects initiated in the real sector of the economy can be conditionally divided into research, industrial and complex, which include both

research and industrial parts [6]. Based on the analysis conducted by the authors, the following typology of innovative projects is proposed.

Research projects (RP index) are aimed at studying the properties of materials, structures and products in order to obtain scientific and technical information, on the basis of which new product designs can be developed or technological processes can be modernized. The result of research and development (R&D) can be a scientific report or technical documentation that is in demand in the innovation market. R&D results are usually patented and can enter the market in the form of a technological or other license, which will be based on an estimate of the costs of research and development.

Industrial projects (IP index) are implemented directly at enterprises that need to develop new types of products and implement new technologies. The result of implementing such projects may be a reduction in the cost of manufactured products, an increase in their output, a reduction in costs, etc.

The project initiator needs investments for its implementation and justification of the relevance of the proposed technical solutions is the first step on this path. And the investor, in turn, must be confident that his investments in scientific research, development, development of new types of products and technologies will pay off and bring profit.

Projects implemented at industrial enterprises may have the following goals:

- development of new types of products (type A);
- implementation of new resource-saving technologies (type B);
- increase in output, expansion of production (type C);
- reduction of the load on the external environment (type E).
- improvement of the organization of production (type D).

It should be noted that the introduction of high-performance technologies does not always lead to an increase in the output of final products, since the need for finished products in subsequent operations may not correspond to the throughput capacity of the equipment installed in adjacent areas.

Projects aimed at developing new types of products (IP-A) are implemented in the following cases:

- the output of traditional products no longer meets consumer requirements;
- the transition to new products allows for significant savings on resources that have become scarce or expensive;
- the consumer qualities of new products are significantly higher than traditional ones and enable consumers to obtain an economic benefit.

New technologies are implemented when it is necessary to reduce resource consumption (IP-B) and to increase output (IP-C), as well as when updating the range of manufactured products (IP-A). If the demand for the products manufactured by the enterprise increases, management decisions are aimed at finding reserves that can be identified using organizational measures, including organizing work in additional shifts, holidays and weekends, reducing breaks, etc. After the effect of organizational measures has been exhausted, investments are attracted to the enterprise for reconstruction and technical re-equipment of the production process. If reconstruction involves modernization of the technological process at existing production facilities, then expansion projects are aimed at building new workshops and other facilities in order to increase output.

Projects aimed at reducing the man-made impact on the environment (IP-E type) are used mainly in foundry or welding production. Metallurgical processes occurring in such technologies as casting and welding are characterized by the release of many toxic compounds into the environment, in connection with which, reducing emissions is an urgent task for designers of technological processes and designers of welding and foundry equipment. Changes in technological processes that reduce or completely eliminate the release of toxic materials and gases make it possible to avoid costs for expensive filtering and ventilation equipment and treatment facilities.

Projects aimed at improving the manufacturing process (IP-D), such as organizing flow lines, optimizing workshop transport flows, reducing downtime, etc., can significantly improve labor productivity and increase output.

Integrated projects (IRP) are typical for industrial enterprises, the structure of which includes research and development departments equipped with laboratory equipment, a testing ground and an experimental design base. Large research and production associations have such capabilities. Most enterprises enter into an agreement with a research and development organization to carry out work on a specific topic, the results of which can be implemented at a specific production site.

Results and discussion

After determining the type of innovative project, it is necessary to prepare a justification for its relevance and scope of application. Relevance is usually understood as the importance, practical significance for an organization or society at the current time of the results of the implementation of a set of measures provided for by a specific innovative project.

Evaluation and justification of the relevance of an innovative project

The most important property of an innovative project is its commercial feasibility. In other words,

the results of the project must be in demand on the market or have a significant public/social effect. Thus, investing resources in upgrading the manufacturing technology of a product whose life cycle is ending due to obsolescence or other reasons will lead to serious losses for the investor.

Thus, it can be concluded that the relevance of an innovative project is determined by the need for products (services) in the current and long-term (forecasted) time period in the domestic and foreign markets. This circumstance emphasizes the need to analyze the demand for products, goods or services specified by the project. The main demand is formed in the domestic market, in connection with which the project initiator must identify the key consumers of the enterprise's final products, assess their ability to purchase additional volumes of new products. If the introduction of a new technology will significantly reduce costs, then, as an option, it is possible to offer the consumer discounts on the price of additionally ordered volumes of goods or services. It is also necessary to study the analogues of the product being developed, manufactured by enterprises competing in this market. Competitors can take such measures to eliminate threats to their business as price discrimination, dumping and other methods of market struggle, which can force the enterprise to reduce prices for its products. The project developer must assess the project's resistance to such threats and propose measures to eliminate them.

To justify the relevance, it is necessary to clearly formulate the expected direct and indirect results of the project. Direct results include resource savings, increased output, increased enterprise revenues, reduced costs, etc. Indirect results are manifested in related areas and become noticeable after some time. Thus, the introduction of a new technology can lead to direct results - increased productivity and indirect results - the release of workers and, as a result, a decrease in injuries and a decrease in the burden on the social and, at the same time, on the innovative infrastructure of the enterprise [7]. Indirect results of the project can also include a decrease in import dependence and the burden on the ecological system, increased competitiveness of the enterprise, etc.

The relevance of a research project is determined by the society's need for information obtained through experiments with materials, database analysis, and intelligent mathematical and semantic modeling of processes [8]. Research in the technical field is considered relevant if the results of R&D will give impetus to subsequent development of new materials, technologies, and products. A systems approach involves determining the sequence of actions of the project initiator to prepare for its implementation at an industrial enterprise.

Preparation of the project investment plan

The preparation of the plan begins with an analysis of the enterprise's production activities, on the basis of which critical problems are identified. This class of problems may include increased resource consumption, wear and tear of the main equipment, manufacturing defects, restrictions in the supply of materials and components necessary for the production of products, a shortage of professional personnel, etc. An indicator that problems have arisen at the enterprise may be an increase in production costs, a drop in product quality, injuries, loss of working time, refusal of consumers to enter into supply contracts, etc. A sign of a critical problem is the fact that its solution enables the enterprise to significantly restore and increase its competitiveness. The sequence of work at the initial stages of implementing innovative projects is shown in Figure 1.

After conducting preliminary marketing research (block 1 of the diagram), as a result of which the demand for the given product is substantiated and a critical production problem is identified (block 2 of the diagram), it is necessary to assess the production potential of the enterprise (block 3 of the diagram), which includes the main and auxiliary equipment, vehicles, buildings, structures, labor and other

resources that can be used in the production of products [9], [10]. The availability of free production areas, warehouses and other structures makes it possible to place equipment and build new sections and lines on their basis.

The most important characteristic of an enterprise is the stage of its life cycle, which is determined by the ability to increase or update the output of products [11]. Implementing an innovative project of the IP type at an enterprise with a worn-out infrastructure will be extremely risky due to possible accidents, logistical failures, restrictions from technical supervision authorities, etc.

At the next stage, the project initiator should study various options for solving the critical problem and select the most suitable ones for the internal and external conditions of the enterprise (block 4 of Figure 1), for which the customer should develop criteria for assessing and selecting project options, which may include the cost of work, the duration of the development and payback period of the project, and the need for certain resources. To make decisions in the unstable conditions in which the Russian economy operates, it is advisable to use methods of game theory and forecasting theory [12].

Fig. 1. Preparatory stage of an investment project of the IP type

Decision making during project implementation

It should be noted that the issues of decision-making in the innovation sphere have been covered in detail in the works of many Russian scientists [13], [14], [15]. The results they obtained can be used to select a specific project option that best meets the established criteria. As an example, let us consider one of the most common methods of decision-making under conditions of incomplete certainty [16].

The following sequence of actions is proposed:

- the most suitable project options that can be implemented at a specific enterprise are selected;
- possible outcomes are preliminarily assessed under certain environmental conditions using expert assessment methods or mathematical modeling;
- the calculation results are entered into the payment matrix of the game with nature (see Table 1).

Table 1

Payment matrix of expected project results

Project option	Variants of the state of the external environment						Mathematical expectation of the result of the implementation of a project variant
	B_1	B_2	...	B_j	...	B_m	
	Probability of the realization of the state of the external environment						
	P_1	P_2	...	P_j	...	P_m	
Expected outcome of the project							
A_1	A_{11}	A_{12}	...	A_{1j}	...	A_{1m}	$M[A_1]$
A_2	A_{21}	A_{22}	...	A_{2j}	...	A_{2m}	$M[A_2]$
...
A_i	A_{i1}	A_{i2}	...	A_{ij}	...	A_{im}	$M[A_i]$
...
A_n	A_{n1}	A_{n2}	...	A_{nj}	...	A_{nm}	$M[A_n]$

By the expected result of the project we mean the possible income (volume of output, profit, costs, etc.) of the enterprise when implementing one of the project options in a certain state of the external environment. The assessment of the possible result can be carried out using the model of the production system developed by the authors based on ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) software solutions [17], [18].

Forecasting methods assess the probability of a particular state of the external environment in which the project is being implemented.

Then the mathematical expectation of each result is calculated:

$$M[A_i] = \sum_{j=1}^m P_j \times A_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where $M[A_i]$ – mathematical expectation of the result of the implementation of a project variant A_i ;

m – number of options;

P_j – probability of realization of the state of the environment B_j ;

A_{ij} – result of the implementation of the project variant A_i under environmental conditions B_j .

The maximum value from a set of options can serve as the basis for making a decision using the Bayes criterion [19]:

$$Ab = \max\{M[A_i]\}, \quad (2)$$

where Ab – Bayesian criterion project variant.

If the state of the external environment cannot be predicted with sufficient reliability, then we use the Laplace criterion to select the appropriate option:

$$Al = 1/m \max \{ \sum_{j=1}^m A_{ij} \}, \quad (3)$$

where Al – variant of the project according to the Laplace criterion [20].

After completing the initial stages of implementing innovative projects, their participants begin to formulate the technical specifications. This document formulates specific indicators for implementing the innovative project, justifies its maximum price, calculates the timeframes for all subsequent stages of work on organizational and technical preparation of production, assesses the need for resources, etc. A detailed description of the approaches used to prepare the technical specifications is beyond the scope of this article.

Conclusions

Based on the results obtained during the present study, the following conclusions are formulated.

The use of a systems approach at the initial stage of designing complex innovative projects for the creation of technical objects and complexes allows the management of high-tech and science-intensive corporations and enterprises to avoid unnecessary expenditure of resources and significantly reduce the time of subsequent work on the technological preparation of production for the development of new types of products.

The typology of innovative projects proposed in the work enables project participants to determine their place in the process. Its practical use will help reduce the level of innovative risks associated with insufficient communication between investors and other participants in innovative projects.

The approaches to substantiating the relevance of an innovative project are substantiated, the sequence of stages of preparation for the implementation of investment plans is determined. To make a decision on the choice of a specific version of the project and its further implementation, it is proposed to use forecasting methods and the methodological apparatus of game theory.

Bibliography:

1. Ayvazyan S.A., Afanasyev M.Yu., Kudrov A.V., Lysenkova M.A. On the issue of parameterization of the national innovation system // *Applied econometrics*. 2017. No. 1 (45). P. 29-49.
2. Varshavsky A. On the strategy of scientific and technological development of the Russian economy // *Society and Economy*. 2017. No. 6. P. 5-27.
3. Russian economy in 2000. Trends and prospects / Edited by E. Gaidar (editor-in-chief), S. Sinelnikova-Murylev. Issue 22. - Moscow: Foundation "Institute of Economic Policy named after E.T. Gaidar", 2001. - 375 p.
4. Russian economy in 2001. Trends and Prospects: In 2 volumes / Edited by E. Gaidar (editor-in-chief), S. Sinelnikov-Murylev. Volume I. (Issue 23). - Moscow: Foundation "E.T. Gaidar Institute for Economic Policy", 2002. - 620 p.
5. Nabiullina E. Statement by the Chairman of the Bank of Russia Elvira Nabiullina following the meeting of the Board of Directors of the Bank of Russia on July 26, 2024. URL: <https://cbr.ru/press/event/?id=18869> (date of access 03/05/2025).
6. Varshavsky A.E. Actual issues of innovative development: problematic innovations // *Analysis and modeling of economic and social processes: Mathematics. Computer. Education*. 2022. No. 29. Pp. 131-145.
7. Khrustalev E.Yu., Larin S.N. Regional priorities in the development of innovative infrastructure // *National interests: priorities and security*. 2011. Vol. 7. No. 42 (135). P. 8-15.
8. Khrustalev E.Yu., Baranova N.M. Intelligent semantic models for improving the quality of educational and research processes // *Economic analysis: theory and practice*. 2013. No. 35 (338). P. 2-10.
9. Golovkin D.S. Industrial enterprise management system based on the concept of economic potential // *Bulletin of the Nizhny Novgorod University named after N.I. Lobachevsky. Series: Social Sciences*, 2020. No. 3 (59). P. 7-15.
10. Belyaeva T.A., Dorokhova T.R., Kozyeva I.A. Assessment of production and economic potential in strategic management of sustainable development of an industrial enterprise // *Bulletin of the South-West State University. Series: Economics. Sociology. Management*. 2021. No. 11 (4). P. 139-150.
11. Slavyanov A.S. Formation of a system of investment support for innovative projects in space activities. Monograph. - Nizhny Novgorod: Professional Science, 2022. - 223 p.
12. Slavyanov A.S. Approaches and methods of game theory in strategic planning of an enterprise // *Controlling*. 2023. No. 87. P. 56-62.
13. Afanasyev M.Yu., Lysenkova M.A. Analysis and comparison of national innovation systems on the example of Russia and a number of other countries // *Strategic planning and development of enterprises: Proceedings of the XX All-Russian Symposium, Moscow, April 9-10, 2019 / Edited by G.B. Kleiner*. - Moscow: CEMI RAS, 2019. Pp. 165-167.
14. Orlov A.I. Methods of making management decisions. - M.: KnoRus, 2022. - 286 p.
15. Kolesnikov A.S. Study of economic aspects of an organization's innovative project: approaches and prospects // *Young scientist*. 2024. No. 41 (540). Pp. 45-47. [Electronic resource] URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/540/118176/> (date of access: 04.04.2025).
16. Vartanov S.A., Ivin E.A. Applied game theory for economists. - Vologda: VolNC RAS, 2020. - 283 p.
17. Slavyanov A.S., Khmyrova E.A. Information support for decision-making based on a production system model // *Controlling*. 2024. No. 94. P. 38-45.
18. Khmyrova E.A., Slavyanov A.S. Information system capabilities under condition of uncertainty // *International Journal of Professional Science*. 2024. № 8-2. С. 18-23.
19. Zamir S. Bayesian Games: Games with Incomplete Information. - Jerusalem: Hebrew University, 2008. - 27 p.
20. Maschler M., Solan E., Zamir S. Game Theory. - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020. - 1025 p.

Дата поступления рукописи в редакцию

15.04.2025

Дата принятия рукописи в печать

18.04.2025